

Research Questionnaire

Delphi Study – Round Three

Project: Heterogeneous Collaboration and Conflict in Spatial Data Co-Production

Ms. Youjin Choe, PhD Candidate

Department of Infrastructure Engineering, Faculty of Engineering and IT

University of Melbourne

Email: ychoe@student.unimelb.edu.au

Supervisors: A/Prof. Mohsen Kalantari, Dr. Martin Tomko

Instruction

This third-round Delphi survey questionnaire contains **five sections**:

- Section A: Personal Information
- Section B: Topic of Conflict
- Section C: Factors Leading to Conflicts
- Section D: Effect of Conflict
- Section E: Potential Conflict Management Method

Please fill out your personal information in Section A, which will only be used for internal identification purpose. **Sections B to E are based on the results from the second-round Delphi survey** (Please refer to *Results of Second Round Delphi Survey.pdf* for more information), **which asks you to rate the importance of each item on a Likert scale**. At the end of each section (B, C, D, and E), you could explain reasons for your rating of importance for each item and/or any anecdotes that you have on the items that you rated as very important. Your response to this questionnaire will be integrated with other survey participants' responses to reach consensus for each section.

Please kindly return the completed questionnaire by 2 November 2021 to Ms. Youjin Choe via email (ychoe@student.unimelb.edu.au).

Your participation to this research is much appreciated.

Section A: Personal Information

Name	
Age range (please mark "X")	Under 18
	18 to 20
	21 to 30
	31 to 40
	41 to 50
	51 to 60
Affiliation (please mark "X")	Over 60
	Volunteering individual
	Corporation (Please specify:)
	Government agency (Please specify:)
	Non-governmental organisation (Please specify:)
Others (Please specify:)	
Geographic scope of interest (for mapping)	

Section B: Topic of conflict

1. Please rate the following topics of conflict in OSM.

First-round results	Not at all important (1)	Slightly important (2)	Important (3)	Fairly important (4)	Very important (5)	No opinion
Tagging						
Border disputes						
AI-assisted mapping						
Organized edits						
Import						
Volunteer mappers vs. others						
Volunteer vs. paid mappers						
Influence of corporate partners						
Diversity and inclusion						
Communication channel						
Code of conduct						

2. Please explain why you rated the items as you did.

Your comment:

3. Please provide any anecdotes on the items that you rated as very important.

Your comment:

Section C: Factors Leading to Conflict

4. Please rate the following factors leading to conflict in OSM.

First-round results	Not at all important (1)	Slightly important (2)	Important (3)	Fairly important (4)	Very important (5)	No opinion
Different personality						
Different cultural background						
Different interest, priority, value, and secondary goals						
Incompatible personality						
Uncooperative behaviour						
"Us vs. them" subgroup						

5. Please explain why you rated the items as you did.

Your comment:

6. Please provide any anecdotes on the items that you rated as very important.

Your comment:

Section D: Effect of Conflict

7. Please rate the following effects of conflict in OSM.

First-round results	Not at all important (1)	Slightly important (2)	Important (3)	Fairly important (4)	Very important (5)	No opinion
Discouraging member participation and motivation						
Lower trust in the community						
No engagement with other members						
Members leaving OSM						
High barrier for new members						
Navigating different interests and opinions						
Toxic atmosphere in the community						
Limited group of members participating in OSM						
Community fragmentation						
Difficulty in building community consensus						

8. Please explain why you rated the items as you did.

Your comment:

9. Please provide any anecdotes on the items that you rated as very important.

Your comment:

Section E: Potential Conflict Management Method

10. Please rate the following potential conflict management methods in OSM.

First-round results	Not at all important (1)	Slightly important (2)	Important (3)	Fairly important (4)	Very important (5)	No opinion
Open communication by corporate partners						
Matured member interaction						
Valuation of diverse participations in OSM						
Shared goal among the members on what OSM is for						
Live member conversation						
Channels for conflict management						
Enforced code of conduct						
Populating OSM working groups						
Improved diversity and inclusion						
Stronger action by OSMF Board						

11. Please explain why you rated the items as you did.

Your comment:

12. Please provide any anecdotes on the items that you rated as very important.

Your comment: